

2023 Astropy Coordination meeting

Wiki with logistics info: <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/wiki/MITMeeting2023>

Main meeting folder: [Coordination2023Notes](#)

Presentations folder: [Presentations](#)

Zoom link:

<https://numfocus-org.zoom.us/j/84003091753?pwd=cnd0WFZyRThOWG1TVWJhRkxDN1BiQT09>

Breakouts: [Breakouts planning 2023](#)

Note: (Kelle says) These notes are neither comprehensive nor should serve as a to-do. Please assign action items as needed in the appropriate place.

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Day 1 (2023-05-02)

Attending (in random order as shown in someones zoom window):

Clara Brasseur, Adrian, David Shupe, Derek Homeier, Eero Vahar, John Swinbank, Larry Bradley, Marten v.k, Perry Greenfield, Stuart Mumford, Thomas Robitaille, Tom Aldcroft, Moritz Günther, Matt Craig, Kelle Cruz, Nadia, Tom Donaldson, William Jamieson, Pey Lian Lim, Timothy Pickering, Nathaniel Starkman, Erik Tollerud, Benjamin Weaver, Wilfred Gee

Agenda

08:30 AM - 09:00 AM: In-person attendees arrive, coffee, building access

09:00 AM - 10:00 AM: Welcome (Moritz Günther), State of Astropy (Kelle Cruz), State of Finance (John Swinbank)

10:00 AM - 11:00 AM: Roadmap: Annual review and discussion of items (Clara Brasseur)

11:00 AM - 12:00 PM: Discussion: Governance of contracts (Moritz Günther)

12:00 PM - 01:00 PM: Lunch + voting for afternoon break-out/coding

01:00 PM - 05:00 PM: Break-out/coding

Introduction (one sentence per person)

State of Astropy

- Presented by Kelle C:
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1VdgcT6NII7g3eLTfopCwe4jIPihO5IPi4GqTzg0Nn8/edit?usp=sharing>
- Stable contributor/commmitter base
- Number of commits seems to be going down a bit
- No peaks before releases any more. Is that a good sign because people don't bunch up at the end? Do the bots help? Or are contributors losing interest?

- Core community already at capacity -> try to increase capacity by hiring -> no capacity to take on hiring. How do we deal with this?
- Have done a few searches (going outside core community) has been successful, but setting that up is a lot of work, hard to find the energy for it.
- Capacity to guide/manage/advise new people is also hard.
 - Breakout: how to deal with this
- Reminder that talks regarding Astropy can/should be placed on Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/communities/astropy>
 - E.g. Erik just put the 2022 ADASS prize talk at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7886508>
- Stats:
 - William/Larry: <https://pypistats.org/packages/astropy>
 - Simon: Some interesting graphs in https://devstats.scientific-python.org/_generated/astropy.html

State of Finance

- Presented by John Swinbank
- \$1.5M reported on. ~500k spent
- Moore grant has ~\$130k left that might evaporate if we aren't creative about spending it
 - Need to be spent, not just promised
 - Suggested breakout: how to spend this money
- Finance committee is interested in feedback on how they do tracking and how much to do

Suggestions for expedited spending of Moore funds

Put ideas here: [☰ Breakouts planning 2023](#) .

Roadmap: Annual Review

- Presented by Clara Brasseur
- Slides: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1pFs5cq4WiErR9wGMwalbb2g522cGh_AYczWLBq4PZw/edit?usp=sharing
- Discussion of possible utility of a project mgr. Noted above in funding ideas.
- In the past, tried to update roadmap day-to-day with issues or other technical solutions, but the problem is the human, not the technology.
- One model (which we've effectively done in the past) is to update every now and then (say once a year) and keep frozen in between.
- Improve support for i/o.

- Could move FITS and HDF5 compression to DONE
- Too much details in here to assign a single status
- Large tables could be its own thing.
- Seems like there's been lots of progress. Potentially no longer a high priority thing.
- Unified i/o system needs TLC - Starkman
 - Maybe a new bullet.
- Needs more discussion and more knowledge.
- Improve support and validation for input and output for standard formats.
 - This will ALWAYS be on the roadmap so I disagree. I think more specific is better. - Kelle
- General support for a generally worded bullet in the roadmap, but there may also be value in calling out more specific high-priority issues/projects
- Improve interoperability.
 - Will always be yellow.
 - Particularly relevant for spectroscopy right now.
- Improve HPC support
 - unclear.
- ARM Macs - DONE
- Interoperability HDF5 and Dask
 - Tom R. - can change to orange. On someone's list.
 - Starkman - going to do it for Quantity. Generate proof of concept.
 - Erik - said something exciting
 - Orange. - plan is not yet clear, but definitely a good start.
- Improve performance, GPUs
 - Should this be about cloud computing instead of GPUs? In addition to.
 - GPU-> "Heterogeneous computing environments (i.e. cloud, GPU, HPC)"
 - This captures the fact that GPUs, many-core CPU, HPC can all be the
 - Big-endian processors should also be grouped in here.
 - Simon - effort happening in numpy
 - "Edge" computing. Edge computing is something like "hybrid between in the cloud and the 'client' side".
- Learn site overhaul - DONE
- Workshop - Stay orange
- Discourse - Reword. stay orange
 - This one needs to be re-worded. It's not just about number and diversity, it's also about engagement.
 - Suggestion: drop what comes after the comma, but add something about "engagement"
 - Maybe add the word "Active" before "user support"?
- Guides/tutorials
 - Progress coming on more this summer.
 - Make green, but add new *ORANGE/RED?* bullet for spectroscopy guide/tutorials. (intertwined with)

- Tutorials for astro courses
 - Need to figure out how to “harvest” rather than “develop”
- Mentoring. Contributor to Maintainer pipeline.
 - Could stay yellow.
 - Controversial, could use a breakout
- Improve inclusion
 - Move to Red
 - Discussion of translation
- Infrastructure and dev documentation
 - This issue about dev documentation captures where we would like to go: <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/issues/11621>
 - See also this stale PR: <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/pull/11840>
- Benchmarking
 - Agree to remove “pull request” part, but not remove bullet point.
- Integration testing for core/coord/infra
 - Change to green
- Define/document categorization of packages
 - A bit unclear, because some of it is defined, but the
 - Agreement to remove this one
- Government, management, and personal — improve process for recruiting...maintainers
 - Need to document how to take on a formal role in the Astropy project or an affiliated package.
 - Agree this needs re-wording
- To add
 - Update/re-think website
 - Improve visibility of Learn
 - Got approval to add to roadmap
 - Figure out how to “publish” and cite tutorials
 - Not adding, but is coming up with the AAS. Could be opened as an issue.
 - Maybe translation?
 - Might be good for community manager to coordinate
 - Seems to fall naturally under the “global engagement” portion of the diversity bullet point. (Wilfred)
 - Open an issue.

Governance of contracts

- Who keep track of what's happening for ongoing things and if it's still in line with what the project wants to do
- In terms of management challenges, it's both on the part of the manager/manager. Does the manager have time/are they being paid for time doing the managing. How onerous is the management on the managee?

- We the project notice too late when things aren't getting done, need project manager to keep tabs.
- The SOC noted during planning of this meeting that there is no language that requires funded individuals to make a presentation of their work anywhere.

Breakout planning

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1laPeE3TkxE_P87cwj6czlbfFaB5pjfKjwPuzgilWlu8/edit#

Breakout: ruff

Who attended: Tom D, Nathaniel, William, Tom A, Ben, Eero, Pey Lian

[Ruff](#) was a new project to centralize linting done on Python projects. Idea to do flake8 1000 times faster, natively implementing most popular plugins. Many big projects use it, like Jupyter. So proposal came up to replace flake8 presence in astropy with ruff. The process actually exposed a lot of tech debt w.r.t. Flake8.

Example PR: <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/pull/14724>

Done so far:

- Turned on flake8
- Hot swapped ruff for flake8 - fail CI if problems
 - Toggle some features off
- Hooked up in pre-commits
 - Pre-commit is run as a bot.
 - Auto-fixing not done, but can be requested when problems found
 - Pre-commits run on server, but can also be run locally by developer
 - Bundled with Black and all linting features in the precommit config.
- Regular suggestions come up for which features to enable in precommits
- Documentation:
https://docs.astropy.org/en/latest/development/workflow/development_workflow.html#pre-commit

Eero: ruff recommends enabling rules as needed, not all at once and then do exceptions (opposite of what we're doing). ruff has a statistics option to see how many lines affected by what rule.

Nathaniel: We use "all" to allow us to build up our own set of rules we like and don't like.

William: Devs are fatigued by the black transition and the ruff enforcing new rules are overbearing.

Problems:

- Increased barrier for new or rusty contributors
- Cost vs benefits to fix the complaints: Is the dev time needed to do this better spent on fixing real bugs?
- Sustainability: When Nathaniel/William unavailable (or become tired of doing it), what happens?
 - Not *too* much effort to just put in exclude rules for any violations.
- It is unclear what needs backporting or not.
- May introduce new bugs if autofix accepted blindly.

Action items:

- Move ruff settings from pyproject.toml to ruff.toml to declutter the former because we put important build info in the former. And we organize ruff.toml by section. Add Nathaniel and William as codeowners for the new ruff.toml – <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/issues/14736>
- ~~Make a “first issue” issue for interested contributors (e.g., professional Python devs who like astronomy) to help fix the ignored stuff.~~
 - Tom A: This could introduce a lot of overhead for core maintainers to review.
 - Instead - hack [APE 2 \(deprecation policy\)](#), [APE 21 \(no more LTS\)](#), and [What is considered a public API?/APE 22](#) session.
- Reduce autofix cadence to monthly. – <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/commit/4b27919041d8e9e2230eadbb6ba1d98bae54d12d>
- Make it clear that this ruff stuff does not automatically apply to coordinated/affiliated packages (opt-in only). – <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/issues/14737>

Outcome:

- Stick with the current policy of selecting ALL rules with explicit opt-out of excluded rules. This requires ongoing maintenance for each ruff release but this is expected to be manageable.

Breakout: Moore money

Who attended:

Kelle C, Matt C, Timothy P, Nadia D, Erik T, Moritz G

- **Hire a part/full time developer.**
 - Perhaps to focus on infrastructure.
 - E.g. through Aperio.
 - One version was [PR #277](#) in Cycle 3.
 - Could be sent to Quantsight and OpenTeams
 - NEEDS A MANAGER and search committee.
 - Wouldn't need a new vote.
 - Mortiz can get subawards (fully loaded) to MIT from NASA.

- Could play a managerial role.
 - Could be an extension of [PR #277](#) in Cycle 3.
- Moritz will make sure he can manage.
- Moritz make the job ad.
- Finance Committee will confirm with Adrian.
 - Note: CCA also planning to hire a software engineer to start in 2024 to work 50% on “community software core utilities” – would be good to coordinate. Value added to have two such positions, but could coordinate mentoring/management/division of responsibilities.
- **Someone to work on the interoperability of ASDF**
 - Institutions and missions which use Java
 - Ed - ex-STScI, currently based in Alaska
 - Make ASDF more language agnostic.
 - Interoperability.
 - Could also be an open hire.
 - Nadia to open an issue.
- Something related to global engagement - Wilfred
 - PL - IAU in South Africa
- Project manager
 - Help with keeping track of roadmap progress
 - Maybe also help with some aspects of contract management
- **Organize a 2-3 day workshop for PhD students and young scholars in Eastern Europe (related to global engagement) - Nadia**
 - Bulgaria
 - Nadia to open an issue. (+Iva and James)
- “More of the same” - continuation of Phase 3
 - **Matt reassign time Fall 2023 + summer salary 2023**
 - Matt to look into it. Extend [#311](#)
 - **Tim for more spectroscopy**
 - Extend [#300](#)
 - Kelle 2023 summer salary - currently on NASA
 - Increase budget for community manager - Kelle
 - Currently \$48k. ([#310](#))
 - Check with other currently funded projects as to whether they can use additional funds.
- LSST/Rubin idea placeholder - Adrian
 - To be filled in or deleted when he has more info and a well-formed description.
- Finance Committee to communicate to all funded projects an opportunity to “extend” their Cycle 3 proposals.

Breakout: LTS (no more), Deprecation Policy, Public API

Who attended: Pey Lian Lim, Tim Pickering, Erik Tollerud, Nathaniel Starkman, Benjamin Weaver, William Jamieson, Tom Donaldson, Nadia Dencheva, Eero Vaher

- Links:
 - [APE 2 \(deprecation policy\)](#) – the changes is part of the same PR to write APE 21
ow
 - [APE 21 \(no more LTS\)](#)
 - [What is considered a public API?/APE 22](#)
- APE 21 is the main goal, but APE 2, APE 22 are needed in support.
 - If APE 21 proposes semantic versioning, and the major version signifies API-breaking changes, what is the (public) API, hence APE 22.
 - Deprecations may get removed in the next 6 months or have to wait over 2 years, depending on when they get in.
 - Are there any astronomical institutions even still use LTS?
 - Ben: From pipeline perspective, they do not want to see something being deprecated (e.g., in v6.3) and only to be removed 6 months later (e.g., in v7.0). But deprecating in v6.0 or v6.1 and then only remove in v7.0 is OK.
 - Deprecation period around one year before removal would be nice.
 - **Proposal: Change major release to yearly instead of every 2 years.**
 - ~~Proposal: Minor release can be less than but no more than 6 months.~~
 - But what about feature freeze?
<https://github.com/astropy/astropy/wiki/Release-Calendar>
 - Only feasible if we automate more.
 - Not now: Maybe future APE.
 - Should we move to date version (e.g., v2023.05.31)? No, will break too many things during transition.
- Erik commented on APE 21:
<https://github.com/astropy/astropy-APes/pull/82#issuecomment-1532023180>
- Tom: Maybe we do not even need a What's New anymore if we can find a way to highlight those things directly in the change log.
- What is public API ([APE 22 that is now a draft PR](#)):
 - We don't want to move modules around just for this.
 - A typical user wouldn't know what “__all__” means.
 - PEP mention of “__all__” as public API was only much later; it was initially about star import.
 - Nathaniel will update his APE 22 PR to recast the APE to tell us where we are now, what is the golden standard, and how to get there.
 - This is a potential cross-discussion with evaluating (or re-evaluating) affiliated packages: we encourage affiliated packages to use the Astropy API, but what happens if part of that API becomes private or disappears entirely (e.g. `astropy.log` or `astropy.utils`)? Do affiliated packages (hypothetically) get penalized because they are not using “enough” Astropy?

- Note: `astropy.utils.iers` is critical to HPC environments. If `astropy.utils` as a whole becomes private, it will need to be moved somewhere public.

Breakout: Governance of contracts + what is a Project Manager supposed to do

Who attended: Moritz, Tom A, Matt Craig, Kelle, Adrian (via phone)

- Governance of contracts + what is a Project Manager supposed to do
 - VOTES: Erik, Moritz, Kelle, TomD, Tom A, Adrian, Matt
 - Contract Technical Representative (COTR)
 - Pool of voting members
 - Some training/guidance would be useful
 - 1 page expectations document.
 - Contract Financial Representative (CFR)
 - “Contract Manager”
 - Scheduling/ensuring contacts between the COTR and the contractor
 - Streamlining the reporting process - where do the updates go?
 - Keep track of who the COTR is for each contract
 - Manager = Finance Committee
 - Contract manager would empower the CoCo to make strategic decisions
 - Would be ideal to organize this into a product: a report which makes it easy for other people to see what has been done.
 - Make connections to the roadmap and grants.
 - We need a pre-defined structure for reporting that everyone uses that makes it easy to aggregate.
 - ACTION on the Finance Committee.
 - First goal is to get a COTR for each current contract
 - NEW CONVERSATION
 - We don't have a Project manager to do the strategic planning, initiatives.
 - The CoCo is not currently empowered/tasked with this.
 - We don't have a good way for other projects/initiatives to engage with us - Adrian
 - Maybe we need to modify [APE0](#) to empower the CoCo to do more “project management”, strategic planning, and strategic partnership.

Day 2 (2023-05-03)

Attending (in random order as shown in someones zoom window):

Quick notes:

- Please put presentations in the [Presentations](#) folder.
- Hard stop at noon.
- Breakouts
 - Side-A on main zoom
 - Will make a zoom breakout room for side-B

Agenda

08:30 AM - 09:00 AM: In-person attendees arrive, coffee, building access
 09:00 AM - 10:00 AM: State of Infrastructure (Pey Lian Lim), State of Learn (Kelle Cruz)
 10:00 AM - 11:00 AM: Reports from [funded projects](#)
 11:00 AM - 12:00 PM: Discussion: Spectroscopy (Tim Pickering)
 12:00 PM - 01:15 PM: Lunch + voting for afternoon break-out/coding
 01:15 PM - 05:00 PM: Break-out

State of Infrastructure (Pey Lian Lim)

Slides: [State of Infrastructure 2023](#)

- Questions about the broken Benchmarks and whether it's only a hardware issue.
 - Both hardware and person-ware.
 - Can potentially be done on github actions.
 - Benchmarking didn't help with LSST adoption (they decided before the benchmarking effort).
 - Ben: For DESI, we are not concerned about the speed of `coordinates`, but we are highly concerned about the speed of `io.fits` and `units/Quantity`. The workarounds are `fitsio` and just not using `units` internally, so we're not really in a "roll your own" situation.
 - Derek: That kind of benchmarking would need to explore (various types of) HPC hardware to be really useful, not just one or two dedicated machines sitting somewhere.
 - Maybe benchmarking can be a potential project for Flatiron RSE that Adrian will hire.
- Pony Factor
 - Over entire lifetime of the project.
 - OK for astropy in general, but small number when drilling down to sub-packages
 - 1-3 for the smaller related packages, such as infrastructure
- Possible Solutions
 - Much discussion.
 - Does hiring someone for a year help? Not in the long term.
 - Upcoming 50% hire at Flatiron
 - Are all parts of the infrastructure equally important or can we do without them? e.g. benchmarks are nice but the project is successful without.

State of Learn (Kelle Cruz, Matt Craig)

- <https://learn.astropy.org/>
- Last meetings ~ Oct 2022, April 2023
- Looking for discussion of priorities
- Jonathan has taken over infrastructure, other participants have scaled back involvement.
- New web page functionality not announced.
- Kelle feels the Learn team gets bogged down in infrastructure.
 - Adrian remarked that these days it's somewhat minimal. Needs continued maintenance but working good enough right now.
 - Hardest thing is content.
- Kelle wants Learn to focus on content indexing of things that are already out there.
- Nathaniel: To make people want to contribute, give them a way to get cited for it.
 - Open issue [astropy-tutorials#158](#)
- Analytics on Learn website:
 - It's recently been dropped, but we have it for the past. Erik will try to get fixed. ([astropy-tutorials#583](#))
- CI for notebooks, i.e. do we know if they always still work.
 - Adrian says they do work with the most recent stable build of Astropy.
 - Can't be guaranteed when indexing notebooks from other sources.
 - Corner case: what if a notebook depends on e.g. `time`, and running the notebook triggers a download of IERS or of the leap-second file. It is possible in principle for the result of a calculation to be different, even if the environment is exactly the same.
- Pey Lian: Re: Harvesting notebooks. I still have concerns (discussed on meeting Slack):
 - 1. As the notebook becomes very specialized (e.g., spectra extraction of a specific instrument), the content would involve using third-party packages that might or might not still work. "Well, it worked when I ran my notebook last year!" Do we then just not accept the content? Or do we accept it with a big disclaimer?
 - 2. Over time, if you do a `==` pin, some upstream package might fix a critical security bug. The affected notebooks would need to update pins, which might also come with API changes that would break the notebooks. We also have no control over this if we index third-party notebooks where the authors refuse to comply. Who checks for this? What happens then; do we un-index?
 - Kelle: These are great questions and all allude to the many challenges of maintaining a high quality learn resource. We have, at least in the past, only accepted/encouraged notebooks which are fairly generic. It's not designed to be the place where you put the example notebook for a particular instrument's reduction pipeline. HOWEVER, we do encourage 3rd party packages from the traditional scientific stack (e.g., `matplotlib`, `scipy`). So, answer to number 1) is accept when package is widely adopted but not accept when material is too niche. The plan is just to bring attention to as many "good" notebooks as possible. I don't think our plan is to do any testing on indexed notebooks (like

those hosted by STScI). If any of those notebooks get so stale as to not be useful, I think we would just un-index them.

Reports from funded projects

	Recipient	Project	Why?
	Aarya Patil	PASEA	Cycle 3
x	Adam Ginsburg	Astroquery Maintenance	Phase 2, Cycle 3
x	Aperio Software	Infrastructure & Core/Coordinated Package Maintenance	Phase 2, Cycle 3
x	Aperio Software	Improving Compressed Image performance and Dask integration in io.fits	Cycle 3
x	Aperio Software	Mentoring	Phase 2, Cycle 3
x	Aperio Software	GUI editable regions	Cycle 3
x	Clara Brasseur	Learn Notebooks	Cycle 3
x	Clara Brasseur	Astroquery Maintenance	Phase 2, Cycle 3
x	Derek Homeier	General Maintenance	Cycle 3
	Jonathan Sick	Learn Astropy Full Stack Development	Cycle 3
x	Kelle Cruz	Project Leadership	Cycle 3
x	Lia Corrales & David Shupe	Learn Astropy Maintenance	Phase 2
x	Lia Corrales & Kelle Cruz	WoCCode	IDEA call
x	Nathaniel Starkman	Astropy.cosmology	Cycle 3
x	Nathaniel Starkman	Units	Cycle 3
x	Ole Streicher	Debian & Ubuntu Packaging	Phase 2, Cycle 3
	Simon Conseil	Gemini	Gemini
x	Tim Pickering	Specreduce / specutils developer	Phase 2, Cycle 3
x	Matt Craig	Photometry guide/image analysis software	Phase 2, Cycle3

- Stuart (Aperio): multiple projects
 - Stuff done on FITS compression support.
 - change how cfitsio is used in astropy - more stable, builds much faster
 - Fits and dask

- Mentoring: Documentation written, but need input from project to pair mentors and mentees, status: stuck a bit. “Easy parts are done, hard parts need to be figures out”
 - GUI editable regions: Not started yet (except for a few investigations into mpl tasks to to)
- Adam: Maintenance, changing APIs, upstream changes, general maintenance work, nothing too exciting.
 - Tom: Astroquery is an example of a successful part of the Astropy project, where major institutions jump in to maintain their own sub-packages; a “crown jewel.”
 - Adam: Brigitta has been a great resource in keeping astroquery infrastructure running.
- Clara:
 - Learn notebooks: astrohackweek (Nov 2022) - quite successful, getting people into writing PRs; building notebooks has not yet started (when semester is over)
 - Astroquery maintenance: Less of the day-to-day stuff, but working through a backlog of PRs, caching overhaul (in particular MAST, TESS caused problems before), de-pandafying contributions (panda hammer!), docs
- Derek: Preparing invoices, fixed timeseries regression, specutils maintenance, GUI regions support vs matplotlib changes, etc,
- Kelle: Coco, Finance committee (weekly telecons, liaising with NumFOCUS), search for committee engagement coordinator, contracts with individuals and institutions (Open Collective is nice), spend most time in finance committee, but not doing the learn projects originally envisioned
- David: Leading AAS workshops for Astropy with 42-45 people per workshop. Contract ended. Erik: Workshops are often unseen in the Astropy community, but have tangible impact on users.
- Kelle for Lia and WoCode: Women who code. Funding from another source
- Nathaniel:
 - https://drive.google.com/file/d/1FAn_WQq90IV514qC41hm9QJ_Vb2dBcjK/view?usp=share_link
 - Cosmology:
 - Next generation using structural subtyping (new in Python 3.8). Makes is easier to use things that are not astropy objects
 - Tom A: Very cool stuff. Maybe can be its own talk.
 - Quantity
 - Similar idea using structural subtypes: e.g. make Column look like a Quantity, but would also work with external packages. Define duck-type protocol, but no need to specify implementation, which would make it possible to pass other unit libraries to pass through astropy

- Should be compatible with NEP 42: <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/issues/13460>
 - In other words: Use composition instead of inheritance
- Ole: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qLOznbKPPP06I5Mcp_Hrko8XVLLZzS5m/view?usp=share_link
 - Debian Astro 4.0 (including a total of ~300 astronomy-related packages) has astropy 5.2.1 for Bookworm (June 2023).
 - Tom A: Brilliant use of funding and great to see what is going on via this update.
- Matt: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1Yj0hTy35br2mg5FLxBNbEB_epdTWgA3UPwg4wxalvRc/edit?usp=share_link
 - Teaching is a major motivation to develop notebooks
 - Jupyter widgets and how to save their state/settings (e.g., astrowidgets)
 - CCD guide running with students. A humanities student used the materials to make a color image of a galaxy.
- Tim: Spectroscopy update can be part of the next session on Spectroscopy.

Discussion: Spectroscopy (Tim Pickering)

Presentation:

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/18PYrwFsNc9N2aGx0tAnHoPIIYW0LnHVVaGNgktr4aHJg/edit?usp=share_link

- STScI is currently involved in both specutils and specreduce development efforts.
- 3rd player in (current) affiliated packages: [SpectraPy](#) (not very active, single developer)
- Proposed affiliated: [Pypelt](#) – very active
 - specutils (Spectrum1D) support in 1.12.2.
 - Lack of modularity and reusability impeding affiliated status
 - Tim plans to take stuff from this package, re-implement upstream in specreduce, and then push that back downstream. Will take work w.r.t. communication and buy-in.
 - Keck lead scientist is also interested in making Pypelt more modular (extra buy-in).
 - Ben: DESI also has very good 2D background sub. But Tim pointed out that it is multi-fiber spectroscopy that is out of scope for Pypelt.
- Others are instrument-specific, like
 - DRAGONS (Gemini) – James: The issue with DRAGONS is not really that it's instrument-specific (in fact it's intended to be quite generic). A lot of the "primitives" are re-used by several Gemini instruments and would be usable by non-Gemini instruments after defining the right keyword mappings etc. The problem is more that the code is too tied to its own pipeline framework, so it's hard just to pull out an algorithm and use it unmodified in a different context, outside DRAGONS.

- [pySpextool](#) (SpeX) – Kelle active in elevating Python/OO features
- Pey Lian: Any roadmap to make specutils and specreduce maintenance more sustainable and done by multiple institutions? Erik: Hard to get buy-in; no roadmap currently.
- Stuart: There is a 1D confusion. This triggered Erik. Ricky is not surprised by the confusion.
 - Erik: Is it useful to do a spectroscopy workshop (e.g., between Astropy and Sunpy)? Stuart said it might be too late now?
 - Kelle: Aspen Summer School for spectroscopy has been proposed that is a month long.
 - Ben: HPC people need to be involved in such workshops and summer schools.
- Perry: Can the useful aspects be extracted from Pypeit and merged with specreduce or another project? It's not ideal, but if they don't want to cooperate, it may be an alternative, and the fact of starting to do so may change their attitude. A quick look at their license makes it look like BSD.
 - Tim has looked at that but found performance bottleneck. They are open but someone else has to do the work; they won't do it.
 - There are also cases where they have not just translated IDL to Python, but then converted it to C code, which may be performant, but then you can't actually look at the Python code.
- Tom R: What if we try and better separate functions that can operate on any NDData subclass that has a spectral axis versus the Spectrum1D etc classes in specutils? We could define a 'spectral-compatible' interface that an object can present, e.g. subclass of NDData with an [APE 14](#) WCS? Stuart "whole-heartedly" agreed. Tom R opened <https://github.com/astropy/astropy-project/issues/339>
 - Erik: But will there be buy-in? Protocol vs implementation.
 - If we cannot get Sunpy to use Astropy stuff, there is no hope.

Break-out sessions

See [☰ Breakouts planning 2023](#) for potential topics

Session 1: 1:15-2:15 pm

Break: 2:15 - 2:30 pm

Session 2: 2:30 - 3:30 pm

Break: 3:30 - 4:00 pm

Wrap-up: 4:00 - 5:00 pm

Breakout: Spectroscopy

Attendees: Erik T, Tim P, Ben W, PL, William J, Nathaniel S, Tom A, Matt C, James T, Perry G, Larry B, others online

- Prior to breakout

- James Turner: Sorry, I had the wrong time zone for spectroscopy (it was wrong on the Wiki...) :disappointed:. Regarding getting involvement from multiple institutions, I'm not sure whether Ben mentioned this, but there has been some recent discussion about co-ordinating work on spectroscopy within NOIR Lab. So far that has just been a few people talking (and not necessarily the people who are actually writing pipelines for spectroscopy AFAICT), but it sounds like NSF is pushing hard to fund a single solution/platform/whatever for DR, rather than different things for each observatory, so this would be something to keep an eye on. I have been trying to remind people (mostly Gemini so far) that we need to collaborate with the wider community and not just NOIR Lab...
 - Ben: Thank you for the reminder. That is indeed the case, and my question about APE 13 below is relevant to that.
 - Gemini has been interested in upstream contributions to specreduce, but has had limited resources.
 - This is also motivated by Astro2020/Decadal Survey and subsequent meetings and discussions. This has created lots of interest, but not yet any new resources.
- Wilfred: For lack of anything else, we can chat about renaming Spectrum1D. I'll admit I am one of those people who would see that name and immediately think it doesn't apply.
 - The "1D" means that there is one dimension of flux that is aligned to the wavelength axis. There could be multiple spectra with the same number of flux pixels aligned with the wavelength axis.
 - ~~Pey Lian~~ Erik will open an issue. – <https://github.com/astropy/specutils/issues/1056>
- Ben: Is [APE 13](#) still current? If not, what is the document to point people to that has a recent description of the state of the development in the various spectroscopy efforts? The target being people who are potential contributors.
 - SpecViz has dropped off, due to the development of other visualization tools, but otherwise it can be considered current.
 - A PR with a such a revision would probably be welcome.
 - It would be worthwhile to list some of the known visualization tools that can serve as a replacement for SpecViz, depending on the use case.
 - Erik volunteered to update APE 13 by removing mention of viz tool. See <https://github.com/astropy/astropy-APEs/issues/83#issuecomment-1534024660>
- Discussion of Pypelt/Astropy interactions
 - Historical review of what as happened
 - Revisit the question of Pypelt vs specreduce
 - Pypelt has a lot of community members due to them having twice-yearly community workshops.

- Pypelt wasn't really imagined as a modular/pythonic tool, unclear if they want to revisit that (depends on who "them" is). They won't do it but they wouldn't say no
- Perry: What if we create a new package and move over core functionality from pypelt over, and then make it affiliated, and tell them they can use this new package too. Given the licensing, we do not need permission but would be nice to have buy-in, but not compulsory.
- William: can we fork it? (Perry too)
 - Erik/Tom: worried that burns a bridge because they'd taken it as a competitor
 - (clarification that forking here means forking and have a "competing" version)
- Straw poll of the room: most everyone was ok with spending \$ on this even if it goes into Pypelt if it is "from" the astropy ecosystem (e.g. specutils, specreduce, gwcs). Finance and Tim will follow up to just make sure we approve this.

Breakout: Code of Conduct

Attending: Matt, Moritz, Tom D

Current [Astropy Code of Conduct](#)

For code of conduct committees and ombudspeople, can we use collective resources of NumFOCUS? Having people more independent of the project may reduce the possibility of delicate interpersonal issues or other conflicts of interest getting in the way.

There was a discussion on NumFOCUS Slack on March 25. This collaboration may be possible, but what actions can/should we take at this time?

Proposal to establish a Code of Conduct joint with other NumFOCUS projects (current proposal written by Moritz (astropy) and Ana (Project Jupyter), looking for feedback and engagement from other NumFOCUS projects and within our own communities):

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/18FnO2E9AJYIQ5llei5A2f4MXprdSIOV-W7-bVc4Q3wY/edit?usp=sharing>

Links to other relevant resources:

- <https://ropensci.org/code-of-conduct/>
- <https://frameshiftconsulting.com/2018/12/10/free-code-of-conduct-enforcement-book-available-now/>
- <https://otter.technology/>
- <https://www.codeforsociety.org/eventfund/resources/crafting-guidelines-for-community-participation>

How do we protect participants and the project from potential legal exposure dealing with CoC issues? Could be useful to just adopt the CoC from another organization such as NumFOCUS if that has been vetted from a legal perspective.

Should we adopt the NumFOCUS CoC. It places much emphasis on in-person meetings. Maybe there should be more content about other forums? It does seem more rigorous than the Astropy CoC.

Looking at specific issues with Astropy CoC:

- How to report?
- Unclear wording about consequences
 - “We will take action when members of our community violate this code such as contacting confidential@astropy.org (all emails sent to this address will be treated with the strictest confidence) or talking privately with the person.”
- What is the process?
 - E.g., when the ombudsperson gets the e-mail, what do they do?
- Lists of things not to do are becoming more common.
- Includes appeals process.

2 new APEs?

- Explicitly adopt NumFOCUS CoC
 - (We may already be obligated to follow it due to our relationship (sponsored project) with them.)
- Work towards a community ombuds/CoC team to curate the guidelines and do the enforcement.
 - A remote team may logistically not be able to carry out certain consequences (banning from Slack, etc.). Do they make a recommendation to the CoCo. Even with our current ombuds system, what authority is given there?
 - For NumFOCUS, the enforcement team consists of the NumFOCUS Board of Directors
 - It may be important for accountability purposes to make public the number of incidents, and especially in how many of those cases the CoCo followed the recommendations of the enforcement group.

Breakout: Type annotation support for astropy

Attendees: Nathaniel S, William J, Tom A, Tim P, Matt C, Tom D, Ben W,

Can start small and incrementally. Some large packages like numpy use stub files to provide a typed interface for users and their IDE's without the need to refactor the whole library.

Discussed [PEP 695](#) about the Type Parameter Syntax. New syntax makes declaring TypeVars implicit which improves readability. E.g.

```
def func[T](a: T, b:T) -> T:
```

```
...
```

Discussion about friction for new contributors. Counterpoint, how many PRs are actually making API changes where they'd have to deal with this. Contributors already have a long list of rules to follow so one more rule isn't that much of a burden.

****kwargs** that get flowed through is an example of where typing can get clumsy. TypedDict is an approach, but requires all keys specified. This all is only an issue when trying to compile the python code. Nothing breaks in the runtime context; works the same as before.

Nathaniel wants to do a POC using utils: <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/issues/14751>

Breakout: Team page revamp (meta issue + open PRs)

Who attended: Pey Lian, Erik, Moritz, Ben, Aarya, Simon

- Looking for ways to make the roles page more “readable” – <https://www.astropy.org/team>
- Discussion of purpose of roles page
 - Consensus we should make it about **what people do** (or what aren't people doing) **not** credit
 - Should reflect how we want things to be, not how they are currently.
 - [PR#532](#) opened to modify webpage.
- Discussion of “grouping” of roles (e.g., Learn, coordinating)
 - Agreement that infrastructure should be a category with some of the roles that exist, and should be expanded to reflect the real large amount of work that infra does
- Dev telecon coordinator is there because when Adrian stopped doing it, no one noticed until we realized dev telecons not happening. Other telecons already tied to specific roles (e.g., infrastructure, Learn, Finance Committee, etc)
- Do **not** want to touch the specific names yet but want to work out some of the roles
- Moritz accepted and rejected the obvious ones following the discussions.
- Actions to be taken going forward in steps:
 - Step 1: Fix the roles without touching names (unless the latter is needed for the former, or is uncontroversial)
 - Expand infrastructure
 - Change Specialist to Project Infrastructure Tech Lead and reduce scope to “set up and maintain CI” and “moving between repo” because others are covered by “core” roles already.
 - Have sub-roles according to broad categories w.r.t. flow chart from State of Infrastructure this morning.

- Move Finance up to after Ombudsperson. No one can deny the importance of money! See <https://github.com/astrophy/astrophy.github.com/pull/535>
 - Remove Madison from all roles as they no longer active and unpaid for a long time by now. See <https://github.com/astrophy/astrophy.github.com/pull/536>
- Step 2: Re-order the roles on the page to be more logical. Right now, the order appears arbitrary. See <https://github.com/astrophy/astrophy.github.com/issues/412>
- Step 3: Add/remove names from the roles based on dev survey response and other means as necessary. Might need guidelines/policies updates (but see APE 0 first).
 - But what if a maintainer no longer has time to do every day tasks but still has very valuable domain specific knowledge and feels a lot of ownership? A new subject matter expert (SME) category?
 - Do we need a more explicit question asking if people want to be removed as part of the 6-month dev surveys?

Day 3 (2023-05-04)

Attending (in random order as shown in someones zoom window):

Pey Lian Lim, Stuart Mumford, Eero Vaher, Wilfred, Perry Greenfield, Tom Robitaille, Clara Brasseur, Matt Craig, Erik Tollerud, Nadia Dencheva, William Jameson, Nathaniel Starkman, Benjamin Weaver, Tim Pickering, Moritz Gunther, Derek Homeier, David Shupe, Tom Aldcroft, Larry Bradley

Agenda

08:30 AM - 09:00 AM: In-person attendees arrive, coffee, building access
 09:00 AM - 10:00 AM: Changed: Affiliated Packages (from proposed breakout topics)
 10:00 AM - 10:30 PM: Discussion: Tasks for Community Manager (Kelle Cruz)
 10:30 AM - 11:45 AM: Future direction of Astropy (astrophy and Astropy) and funding. *How do we stay hip?* General discussion on mindset and ideas about community, funding, proposals, not technical roadmap. (Erik Tollerud)
 11:45 AM - 12:00 PM: Discussion: Location for next year Coordination meeting
 12:00 PM - 01:00 PM: Lunch + voting for afternoon break-out/coding
 01:00 PM - 05:00 PM: Break-out/coding

Impromptu hack session: Typing: <https://mit.zoom.us/my/hamogu>

- Walking through adding types to `astropy.utils.misc` as a way to see what typing looks like in practice.
 - Positives:
 - Quickly ran into a case where the API wasn't defined in the docstring, so adding types was an improvement
 - Also found a case where the docstring doesn't reflect the types actually allowed based on the code in the function
 - Rapidly ran into a case where code is likely outdated and has some conditionals left over from Python 2.
 - Negatives:
 - Brief discussion of TypeGuard because the first function we tried to type is a type guard function (it tests to see whether an object is iterable), for which there is more extensive typing possible by specifying what type the function is checking for.
 - Adding typing for arguments that get passed into numpy can be hard because numpy is still in the process of implementing typing.
 - Had to write some custom types for some arguments
- Stick with documented API when there is documentation and when the

Affiliated packages

- How to update/increase review pool for Affiliated Package requests
 - Reviewers are anonymous by default; so any new process has to respect this.
 - Derek: The list has been mainly generated from people active in the project, whose research interest matches the affiliated package AFAIK; but could use an update/better structure. I think the list itself may not need to be private as long as the reviewers actually picked remain confidential.
 - Pey Lian: If we have a small number of people, anonymity cannot be guaranteed if we make the list public as people can do their own deduction.
 - Spreadsheet inherited from Tom R., et al.
 - **Action:** Moritz has updated the 6-month survey to include a question for people to add/remove themselves, then Editors will take these results to update the list. (Done.)
 - **Action:** Update the review process document to indicate or point to the procedure for updating the list of available reviewers.
<https://github.com/astropy/astropy-project/issues/340>
 - Crowd-source identification of additional reviewers to people receiving the survey?
 - Current rules say "The pool of available reviewers will be anyone who has an official role on [the Astropy team](#) or anyone who has participated in the

Astropy project enough to be familiar with the project guidelines and requirements”

(https://github.com/astropy/astropy-project/blob/main/affiliated/affiliated_package_review_process.md) - which is in general the people who get the roles survey or got it in the past

- Do we really have a problem finding reviewers?
 - Derek: Yes, those are cases where I have been turned down by people, because they were just too busy (and understandably, since some things came down to the same 2-3 people).
- How does a project get affiliated? (Turns out this is also part of the roadmap)
 - **Action:** Form a Working Group to reach out to JOSS and pyOpenSci. (Pey Lian put this on CoCo agenda.)
 - When should one even think about applying?
 - What is unclear in [Affiliated Package application procedures](#)?
 - How do packages *stay* affiliated? Is the evaluation rubric the same in 2023 as it was in 2017 for example?
 - What does our Affiliated scheme offer that others like JOSS and [consolidating with pyOpenSci](#) do not already?
 - Review by JOSS/pyOpenSci first, *then* apply for affiliation?
 - <https://www.pyopensci.org/software-peer-review/about/our-goals.html>
 - They have a “domain” idea, so maybe we can reach out and see.
 - <https://joss.theoj.org/>
 - **Action:** Adrian: We should reach out to *both* JOSS and pyOpenSci. JOSS has the reviewers that we can tap into that pyOpenSci might not have.
 - Identify the additional criteria on top of JOSS/pyOpenSci; make sure that complying with Astropy criteria does not trigger a re-review by JOSS/pyOpenSci, *i.e.* orthogonal criteria.
 - JOSS requires a paper, but it can be very short, *e.g.* two paragraphs.
 - Passing pyOpenSci is similar enough to JOSS that the only additional requirement would be the paper.
 - Erik: But the current process is to foster a sense of community, what we promised them from the start.
 - Ben: How to maintain Affiliation (and therefore remain in the community) is a more important topic than the initial review process (whether status quo or the new way). Adrian agrees.
 - Tom: Would ease the process for us if we collaborate with them.
 - Pey Lian: What to do with those already Affiliated and the ones under review.
 - Can we automate some of the criteria checks?
 - This would also help in the re-review because we certainly do not have the resources to manually re-review 40+ existing affiliated packages.

- Derek: how do we define “stable”?
 - “Nebulous”
 - See how packages look a few years after review.
- Affiliated Package Support in [Debian Astro](#)
 - Ran out of time, but here’s some data on the existing situation:
 - Architectures supported by [Debian](#).
 - Are affiliated packages aware of the architectures that are supported?
 - Packages that are not in Debian Astro:
 - Coordinated: no packages missing.
 - Affiliated: agnpy, baseband, BayesianFitting, cluster-lensing, dust_extinction, Halotools, HENDRICS, hips*, kanon, lensastronomy, ligo.skymap, linetools, marxs, mocpy, omnifit, PyCBC, pyspeckit, Saba, sbpy, SpectraPy, spherical_geometry, statmorph, stingray.
 - *A Debian package exists but upstream is inactive.
- Package Template
 - Ran out of time. Probably worth a breakout or separate working group.
- ASDF as an affiliated package
 - Ran out of time. Application from them required/expected.

Community Manager

- Original proposal: [Community Manager.md](#)
- Relevant issue to track progress: [astropy-project#310](#)
- [Job ad](#) on NumFocus Job board
- Priorities to add
 - Reach out to communities not well represented in the Astropy Project, who are or are potentially user: professional astronomers outside US/Europe
 - Facilitate workshops at international conferences
 - Use IAU mailing lists to advertise
 -
 - Reach out to communities not well represented in the Astropy Project, who are or are potentially user: Amateur astronomers
 - Reach out to communities not well represented in the Astropy Project, who are or are potentially user: Instructors who use astropy for their courses
 - Coordinating translation/i18s efforts for documentation

Tasks: Assign priorities 1-5 where 1 is HIGHEST Priority here:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1VCxD7-0cjxVUBXiiE6nYUpNmXwrV3jlaqq5uQYsR2NE/edit?usp=sharing>

- Monthly updates requested by NumFOCUS for their newsletter
- Discourse, Stack Exchange, and Facebook group moderation and crossposting
- Slack moderation and crossposting
- Twitter post of announcements and replies to mentions
- Help with Coordination Meetings

- Help expanding workshops to more varied users
- Help publicizing Learn Astropy resources
- Coordinating website content refresh and updates with web site maintainers
- Community and/or User Survey
- Coordinate update to the Astropy Code of Conduct
- More regular updates on a blog or the main Astropy website

Future direction of astropy

Slides:

Discussion

- Some discussion during the talk on languages already
 - Running Python in a browser is getting traction (WASM)
 - Interaction with other languages is getting easier, top contenders are
 - Rust
 - Julia (?)
 - Fortran (clearly!)
- Open Astronomy was created to be broader than Python – keep that in mind as we look at broadening
- Tom R: Performance and maintaining a stable API no matter how hip we wanna be.
- Pey Lian: Maybe prioritize cloud and WASM compatibility if we have to pick and choose? We cater to different demographics and they have different requirements (students vs institutions).
- As the language evolves how and when do we refactor whole modules, making breaking changes.
- Tom D: We should pick what is important even if it seems tough and worry later. Javascript was slow until some company with money came in and thought this would be really useful if faster, and made it happen.
- Tom A: What did Doug Finkbeiner mean about community? Project sets an example by having discussions about technical discussions in public.
- Kelle: Broader astro community appreciates the development effort done at astropy.
- Tom A: The Python in Astro ecosystem is much larger than astropy and affiliated packages – do we need to try to unify that?
- Wilfred: There are a much broader array of devices coming on line (internet of things, satellites, etc)
- Nathaniel: Money: Astropy has been good in centralizing. Can we go big and help with resources (more funding!) to unify more packages to reduce double efforts?
- Benjamin: Especially as platforms proliferate we need to look more closely at reproducibility across platforms and across time
- Nathaniel: We have 5 or 6 different ways we need to compile code already....do we really want to add rust on top of that? Ask ChatGPT to turn our C into rust.
- Adrian PW: On affiliated packages, two highly-used Python astronomy packages that build on astropy and believe in the "mission" but aren't affiliated are [Lightkurve](#) and

[dustmaps](#). Possible case studies for understanding the future of affiliated packages / whether the concept is still needed as it has been defined, or if the community has outgrown it because it is doing what we want naturally.

- Tom R: One example of a place to try rust is in astropy.stats, where we have a short Cython file that turns into huge C code that takes a long time to compile. Convolution is another place we could improve things.
- Tom D: CDS has coded several useful astronomy functions in Rust:
<https://github.com/cds-astro?q=&type=all&language=rust&sort=>
- Pey Lian: Since we can't beat ChatGPT (or CoPilot) we should join it
 - AI miss subtle things or can be subtly wrong. How do we fix that? For example, can we tell user like "you need to prompt it like this to get the more correct answer"?
- William: infrastructure to build rust into wheels (generally easier than for C).
- Moritz: rust-added user-side dependencies (not an issue with wheels)
- Nathaniel: Things like GitHub CoPilot understand structure, which is another important reason to clarify API.

Next Coordination Meeting

Need to do hybrid again, so whatever we choose need to support **hybrid** mode.

Who is hosting in 2024?

- **Nathaniel Starkman** ([University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada](#)) but need to ask mhvk; some international people can access that country more easily than USA
- **Wilfred Gee** ([Subaru Telescope, Hilo, Hawaii](#)), still USA but can cater to Pacific area, but timezone is very inconvenient for Europe
- **Lorentz Center** ([Netherlands](#)) has a small venue that might be appropriate for a coordination meeting, they have professional LOC but deadline is **2023-05-30**, and we actually have to apply and wait, but may not get it. But maybe we shouldn't because Python in Astronomy is also applying...
- **Stuart Mumford** ([United Kingdom](#)), "I would be up for reaching out to [SKA](#) to see if they would be interested in hosting, I know they were pre-pandemic."
- **John Swinbank** ([ASTRON, Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy, Netherlands](#)), "ASTRON is one of the partners in constructing the SKA, but I'm guessing Stuart means SKAO, the project HQ in the UK. (There isn't really an organization just called 'SKA'). That said:
 - If we want an NL location which is not the Lorentz Centre, there are a bunch of options. I can almost certainly find us a venue.
 - Although I don't work for SKAO, I work closely with a bunch of people there, and would be happy to help coordinate."

How do we decide?

- Is it CoCo or SOC who make the decision?
- Tom A: People need to be able to vote; see who is actually planning to go or not.

- Ranked choice voting. If we don't get first choice, we automatically fall back to second, and so on.
- Nathaniel: International location is nice but where does the money come from?

Who is going to be on SOC?

- Tom R: I'd be happy to join the SOC for next year if we still need volunteers, but if there are already enough people just ignore me.
- Tim P: I'd be happy to help as well...

Breakout: astrowidgets

Who attended: Pey Lian Lim, Erik Tollerud, David Shupe, Matt Craig, Moritz Gunther(?), Tim Pickering(?)

<https://github.com/astropy/astrowidgets>

David would like to discuss Firefly backend / base class

- How to add Firefly as a backend to astrowidgets?
 - astrowidgets is favoring [protocol](#) over base class.
- Is there still room for more backends? Yes!
 - But we're thinking the backend implementation would live in the actual backend packages, though they should follow the protocol that astrowidgets set.

Some established API (e.g., `viewer.load_fits(...)`) does not make sense when in actual implementation (e.g., `Imviz` in `Jdaviz`), the loading is done at the app viewer, not viewer level. In fact, the app is allowed to have multiple viewers while its data collection is app-wide.

Who is the target audience of astrowidgets API?

- Erik says the users are astronomers who don't need/want to understand details of backends, and people writing notebooks who want the same
- Matt says it's also the devs who are writing tools and want to enable the people above to do stuff

What if we define a second protocol (e.g., data loading) that makes sense for the layer above viewer?

I.e. in addition to current `Astrowidget` class, there's also a `DataLoader` protocol that has `load_fits`

Can we simplify all the different load methods (e.g., `load_fits`, `load_array`) into a generic one (`load`)? Yes, although some discussion of `load_File/load_data` vs `load`

- A lot of time spent on arguing over whether astrowidgets should enforce what file formats all backends need to support.

WE AGREED: we want to use the protocol style interface

WE AGREED: load_* -> "load"

WE AGREED: backends should live outside the astrowidgets repo

ACTIONS: Matt will break out the protocol part in a new branch in astrowidgets, Erik will split that out into two classes, Pey Lian will do a proof of concept against either ginga or imviz (if Erik can convince her PO to give her the time)

API currently at: <https://github.com/astropy/astrowidgets/pull/147>

PR that currently includes Protocol + bqplot: <https://github.com/astropy/astrowidgets/pull/142>

Breakout: astropy.units and other implementations

Who attended: Benjamin Weaver, Tom Donaldson, Eero Vaher, Nathaniel Starkman

- [NEP42](#) and [astropy/astropy#13460](#)
 - Updating units will prepare for the future
- Replace with [pint](#), or something similar?
 - Both pint and astropy have similar concepts of Quantity.
 - However there is a lot of dynamic class creation in pint. A LOT.
- `astropy.units.Unit` and related objects are not actually related by inheritance.
- Hide new private API behind `astropy.units.Unit`.
- Decomposition can be slow, but a `pint`-like structure can speed this up.
 - Deferred decomposition may also be possible.
 - In principle make this independent of `numpy`.
- A unit may need a coefficient, not just a power of 10.
 - Or a zero-point offset: looking at you Celsius & Fahrenheit.
- Replacement for units needs to satisfy reproducibility tests with current implementation.

Breakout: Brainstorming responsibilities / scope of work for a new RSE hire at CCA

Who attended: Moritz, Nathaniel, William, Pey Lian, Adrian, Kelle

Where: **MAIN ZOOM**

Adrian can't join until ~2:45/3

Two hires, both have their own CCA specific jobs and only work a fraction ($\leq 50\%$) in Astropy

- 1. Low level language kinda person (MESA?)
- 2. Community tools kinda person

Brainstorming responsibilities / scope of work for a new RSE hire at CCA

- Balance of infrastructure / watching for fires vs. bigger "projects" and new development (e.g., spectroscopy)

- Things that are easy to track, at least in the beginning, to be able to check that onboarding and mentoring needs are recognized
- Pick something that does not set a new person up for failure, i.e. does not require specific domain knowledge
- Onboarding phase:
 - Don't start with things that need maintainer privileges; we expect that person to become a maintainer, but need to start out to get into the community
 - Start with something that's getting eye's on the code. Would see every piece of code, get to know all the maintainers, intro to the community, e.g.
 - Typing
 - Triaging
 - doc update
 - Benchmarking
 - Find slow tests and mark them as slow
- Longer term responsibilities (menu, not do all of them)
 - Roadmap
 - Co-maintainer of coordinated packages, e.g. support CCDproc
 - Spectroscopy / specreduce
- Infrastructure
 - Current infrastructure team can't necessarily guide the person
 - Pey Lian: I wouldn't know what is high priority on top of my head at this moment. We just have so much accumulated technical debt.
 - Moritz: <https://github.com/astropy/sphinx-automodapi> is one of my favorites with a number of open issues, no specific astronomy knowledge required and potentially very broad applicability (even outside of astronomy)
- Core:
 - Subpackage that aligns with CCA interest: coordinates, timeseries
- Learn:
 - Producing CCA contents
 - Helping with workshops

Adrian: Someone from CoCo should volunteer for CCA hiring committee. Adrian will ask the other committee on what skillset is desirable from CoCo member.

- Kelle also has contract with Flatiron, which might or might not be desirable; Adrian will ask.

Breakout: Make IERS handling more robust

Who attended: Erik, Tom A, Ben W, Tom D, Eero V, Tim P

Where: <https://mit.zoom.us/my/hamogu>

Make IERS handling more robust

- However there is still the issue that sometimes you do want to download IERS updates and the server is down. The IERS download could handle this case more robustly.

- Ben W is interested in upstreaming some code that performs all the [recommended IERS “turn-off” steps](#) in a single utility function.

Notes

- People are mostly here either because they are people who feel responsible for IERS or because they don't want to have to deal with the IERS failures when the downloads don't work
- Tim P has an observatory that operationally finds it a headache to get it working
- Ben W has a workaround in HPC contexts and wants to upstream.
 - <https://github.com/desihub/desiutil/blob/main/py/desiutil/iers.py>
 - <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/issues/14757>
- There was some realization that the configuration items that currently exist might let the observatories do what they need but they are on older versions. So might be a problem that is solved but there's a lag in people realizing it
- People should be prepared to have workarounds if high accuracy is urgently needed.
- What we could do is download a small update and paste it onto the IERS-B file that is bundled with astropy (eopc04.1962-now)
- AGREEMENT: we are willing to change the contract our users, especially given APE21 changes in timescale. We think not auto-downloading for at least 1 year will work if we package IERS_A with astropy. Need to check with @mhvk though - need to open issue
 - <https://github.com/astropy/astropy/issues/14756>
- Not sure if there's agreement: how to deal with leap seconds
 - But maybe there won't be for a long time (2035)? But no guarantees.